

Population Viability Analysis of the Western Snowy Plover.

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Abstract

A key component to adaptive management of threatened and endangered species is periodic updating of recovery goals and management priorities after implementation of previous management strategies. This report describes an updated metapopulation viability analysis for the distinct population segment (DPS) of western snowy plover (*Charadrius nivosus nivosus*) breeding on the U.S. west coast based on monitoring data from across its range for the 12 years after the population's recovery plan was published. Analysis of demographic data from five to nine sites spanning the U.S. Pacific coast revealed latitudinal gradients in both adult survival and fecundity, with plovers from southern populations experiencing greater longevity and producing higher numbers of chicks than plovers from northern populations. These latitudinal gradients in demographic rates resulted in a geographic pattern in population growth potential, with sites south of Point Reyes National Sea Shore expected to be population sources, and most sites north of Point Reyes expected to be sinks. High adult survival of Oregon birds relative to other northern populations meant that Oregon sites also had relatively high potential growth rates for their latitude. Once dispersal was accounted for, all sites except those in northern California (Recovery Unit 2) and Washington had positive potential growth rates, with populations in southern and central California acting as strong sources ($\lambda \gg 1$). Simulated plover population dynamics were quite stable through time and across replicates, with an average metapopulation size of ~1950 birds. Mean metapopulation size in simulations was more sensitive to adult survival than either fecundity or juvenile survival. Increasing environmental stochasticity had little effect on mean metapopulation size, but large effects on both predicted year to year fluctuations and model uncertainty. Only simulations without dispersal or with continuous habitat loss predicted a sustained decline in plover populations. Overall, intensive predator management across the range coupled with source-sink population structure has substantially reduced the risk of extinction for western snowy plovers as long as current management practices continue and sufficient high quality habitat remains available. However, a single demographic target across the range may be inappropriate, as overall metapopulation dynamics are contingent on high growth potential of southern populations, while lower growth potential in northern populations means that greater effort will be required there to achieve the same growth rate. No simulations reached the 3000 plover target set forth in the current recovery plan. Reaching this target will likely require habitat restoration and more consistent use of currently unoccupied sites. In addition to continued aggressive predator management, plover recovery will require a better understanding of 1) mechanisms through which density dependence acts on plovers and environmental variables that determine habitat suitability, 2) how much dispersal occurs between populations and what influences dispersal rates and distances, and 3) mechanisms underlying latitudinal patterns in demographic rates and how those mechanisms will shape the species' response to global climate change.

Introduction

The Pacific coast breeding population of western snowy plover (*Charadrius nivosus nivosus*) has been listed as threatened population since 1993 under the Endangered Species Act. Since 2005, the estimated breeding population size has varied between 1,537 and 1,877 adults. Currently, most of the U.S. Pacific coast plover population breeds in a few large subpopulations in central and southern California while plovers occur at lower densities in Washington, Oregon and northern California.

Snowy plover recovery goals include threat reduction and numerical targets for population size and fledgling production. Population size goals are based on expert opinion and historic counts of breeding and wintering birds at beaches along the Pacific coast (USFWS 2007). The productivity target is based on a metapopulation viability analysis (MPVA) that was conducted in support of the recovery plan (Nur et al. 1999). This original MPVA made two assumptions based on plovers having a population structure typical of classic metapopulations. First, all vital rates within and dispersal rates among all recovery units are the same if predator management is conducted at similar intensity among them. However, several recent observations suggest that plover population dynamics exhibit a different type of spatial structuring. First, studies of dispersal from Monterey and northern California indicate that although birds are capable of dispersing from one end of the species' range to the other, dispersal is much more likely to occur to nearby than to far away populations (Stenzel et al. 1994, 2007, Colwell et al. 2007, Pearson and Colwell 2013). Second, there is some evidence that plovers may instead exhibit a source-sink dynamic in which highly productive source populations support sink populations that would perish in the absence of immigration (Eberhart-Phillips and Colwell 2013).

Additionally, Nur et al. (1999) assumed that all populations fluctuate independently. However, there are several reasons to suspect population dynamics may be spatially correlated in ways that have implications for metapopulation persistence (Harrison and Quinn 1989). Climatic events, such as unusually cold or wet springs associated with El Niño and La Niña events (Schonher and Nicholson 1989, Morrison and Bolger 2002) are likely to affect many if not all populations along the U.S. west coast. Intermixing of birds from different breeding populations at wintering grounds offers additional opportunities for climatic events to impact populations across the range. In addition, dispersal among sites may synchronize local population dynamics that would otherwise fluctuate independently (Ranta et al. 1995).

We use data from across the range of western snowy plover to 1) determine spatial patterns in population dynamics and demographic rates, and 2) conduct an updated population viability analysis to inform recovery. A detailed analysis of spatial synchrony in plover population dynamics is provided in the accompanying report (Eberhart-Phillips et al. 2013). Three recent papers (Stenzel et al. 2007, 2011; Mullin et al. 2010) have provided much more detailed information on annual variation in adult and juvenile survivorship. Similarly, data on plover reproductive output are now published in a variety of papers (e.g., Neuman et al. 2004, Colwell et al. 2010). Lastly, increasing information on dispersal of individual plovers (Stenzel et al. 1994, 2007, Colwell et al. 2007, Pearson and Colwell 2013) along the Pacific coast enhances our ability to model the role that immigration and emigration play in shaping the persistence of local populations (Mullin et al. 2010).

Plover life history The threatened plover metapopulation of the U.S. occupies habitats within 80 km of the Pacific Ocean from Damon Point, Washington (46°56'29"N, 124° 6'43"W) to the Tijuana Estuary, California (32°32'4"N, 117° 7'25"W). The plover's range on the Pacific coast extends into Baja California, Mexico (Palacios et al. 1994). Breeding habitats include sandy ocean-fronting beaches and suitable portions of adjacent dune systems, dredge spoil islands, salt pannes, active and retired salt evaporators, and, atypically, riverine gravel bars, bay-fronting beaches, and active and pond margins near the coast. Snowy plover breeding typically occurs from March, when the first eggs are laid, until September, when the last chicks fledge (Page et al. 2009). Plovers have been described as a partial migrant, with some individuals residing year-round at their breeding site whereas others migrate (Warriner et al. 1986, Stenzel et al. 1994, Colwell et al. 2007). Most juveniles settle within 50 km of their natal site (Stenzel et al. 2007, Colwell et al. 2007). Adult dispersal is common among sites within or between successive breeding seasons (Stenzel et al. 1994, Colwell et al. 2007). The majority of these movements occur at distances less than 200 km (Stenzel et al. 1994, Pearson and Colwell 2013).

Methods and Results

Data analyses

Demographic data were compiled from recent publications, reports to USFWS, breeding window surveys (BWS; an annual single, range-wide survey for breeding adults carried out primarily within a one-week time frame in mid to late May) and directly from organizations monitoring plover breeding grounds. These data were used to estimate the following demographic rates entered into the model (Figure 1):

- *fecundity*: the average number of chicks hatched per male at a site in year t
- *local juvenile survival*: the probability that a nestling survived its first year and did not emigrate to another site
- *local adult survival*: the probability that an adult bird survived from year t to year $t+1$ and did not emigrate to another site
- *juvenile emigration rate*: the probability that a nestling survived its first year and emigrated to another site
- *adult emigration rate*: the probability that an adult bird survived from year t to year $t+1$ and emigrated to another site
- *distance dispersal probability curves*: the probability that a dispersing bird immigrates to a destination site given the distance between the destination and the site from which it originated.

For the most part, sites correspond to breeding sites listed in the BWS. However, some data came from sources covering several nearby BWS sites and were reported without further breakdown. In such cases, "site" refers to the area covered by the data source and locations were determined as approximately the midpoint of the corresponding latitudinal range. A complete list of data sources and the analyses to which they contributed presented in Table 1.

Because different agencies and organizations used different monitoring methods to collect and report data, demographic rates were first estimated for each year at each site for which data were available.

We then used these estimates in further analyses of spatial-temporal patterns in demographic rates. The statistical analyses described below were designed to determine functional relationships supported by the data to be entered into the model. These relationships are based on hypotheses about how demographic parameters might vary over space and time for the purpose of extrapolating results from the subset of sites where data are available to other sites along the U.S. Pacific coast. These analyses are not designed to test specific hypotheses and should not be interpreted as evidence for specific mechanistic drivers.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for plover metapopulation model. Arrows indicate contributions to the number of plovers in population A next year by plovers in population A, nearby population B and distant population C. Width of arrows indicate relative influence of each process. The associated model parameters are local adult survival (s_{ad}), fecundity (male chicks/male adult, $\frac{1}{2}f$), local juvenile survival (s_{juv}), adult emigration (e_{ad}), juvenile emigration (e_{juv}), and distant-dependent immigration (i).

Table 1. Data sources used in demographic analyses to parameterize metapopulation model.

Adult survival	
capture histories	Northern California 2001-2010 San Francisco Bay 2008-2011 Monterey Bay 2001-2012 Oceano Dunes 2003-2011 Vandenberg AFB 2003-2011
return rates	Oregon 2001-2012
Juvenile survival	
capture histories	Northern California 2001-2010 San Francisco Bay 2008-2011 Oceano Dunes 2003-2011 Vandenberg AFB 2003-2011
return rates	Oregon 2001-2012 Monterey Bay 2001-2012
Chick production	
total chicks by known number of breeding males in sites with most breeders banded or small enough population to allow accurate count	Oregon 1992-2012 Northern California 2001-2010 Point Reyes 1995-2011 Monterey Bay 2001-2012 Bolsa Chica 1997-2011
total chicks divided by number of males estimated as maximum number of simultaneously <u>known</u> active nests	NB Coronado 2000-2011 Pendleton MCB 1999-2012 Oceano Dunes 2002-2012
total chicks divided by number of males estimated from BWS	Vandenberg 2002-2012
Distance dispersal curves	
reported immigrants	Bolsa Chica 1997-2011 Oceano Dunes 2002-2012 Vandenberg 2002-2012 Monterey Bay 1997-2012 Oregon 1992-2012
juvenile dispersal	Monterey Bay 2001-2013
Emigration rates	
% birds dispersing >10 km between nest attempts	Pearson and Colwell 2013
% marked birds known to disperse	Pendleton MCB 1994-1999
exchange of banded birds between Oceano Dunes and Vandenberg AFG	Oceano Dunes 2003-2012 Vandenberg AFB 2003-2012
published dispersal rates	Stenzel et al. 2007 Stenzel et al. 1994

Adult survival: Adult survival estimates came from two sources. Estimates from Oregon came from return rates included in annual monitoring reports to USFWS, which represent the joint probability that a marked bird survived from year t to year $t+1$, returned to Oregon during the breeding season of year $t+1$, and was observed in year $t+1$. Estimates from Northern California, San Francisco Bay, Monterey Bay, Oceano Dunes and Vandenberg come from analysis of mark-resight data from each site and thus represent the joint probability that a marked bird survived from year t to year $t+1$ and returned to the same area in year $t+1$, while detection probabilities were estimated directly from the data. Each site was analyzed separately. Several models making different assumptions about survival and detection probability were fitted using the Cormack Jolly Seber method as implemented in Program MARK (v7.1). The assumptions tested were that:

- survival varied by year
- survival varied by class, with classes being the first year after marking and all subsequent years
- survival varied by class and year
- survival was the same for all birds in all years

and:

- detection varied by year
- detection was the same for all birds in all years
- detection rates differed between the first year after “capture year” and subsequent years (i.e., varied by class)

Although previous studies have shown that adult survival varies by sex (Stenzel et al. 2007, 2011, Mullin et al. 2010), sex was not included in models as not all data sets included reliable sex determination of individual birds. All combinations of the four survival models and first two detection probability models at all sites were tested. The third detection model was only paired with the top survival models with and without class variation in survival.

We used the model-averaged yearly estimates from each site to evaluate whether local adult survival rates varied among sites or years within a general linear model framework or, for nonlinear functions, by nonlinear regression. All analyses were conducted using program R (CRAN). The resulting AICc values were used to evaluate the support for different models describing different hypotheses (Burnham and Anderson 2002). We tested models assuming that survival: 1) was constant across all sites and years, 2) varied by year but not site, 3) was unusually low in 2006—corresponding to an 18% decline in the BWS range-wide population estimate— but did not otherwise vary across years, 4) was lower between 2001-2003 than between 2004-2012 (as a way to address a general increase in predator management after 2002-2004), 5) varied by latitude (measured as km north of the U.S./Mexico border), 6) varied by site independent of latitude, 7) differed by latitude with an exception for Oregon birds, and 8) all appropriate 2-way interactions. We included models with linear, exponential and logarithmic relationships between survival and latitude.

Juvenile survival: Juvenile survival data came from the same sources as adult survival, except that data from Monterey Bay were from the return rates included in their 2004-2009 reports and from Stenzel et

al. (2007). The capture histories from Vandenberg and Oceano Dunes sites were based on band-combinations of juveniles banded by brood, such that a juvenile reported to survive could be any of up to 3 birds (average banded brood size was 2.7 chicks). We corrected for this by adjusting the estimated survival as $s=1-(1-s^*)^{(1/2.7)}$, where s^* is the survival of at least one of the cohort, and $(1-s^*)^{(1/2.7)}$ is the probability that all members of a cohort died. Capture histories from San Francisco Bay and Northern California were of individual birds, so we did not apply corrections to those estimates.

Note that fledgling success (i.e., the probability that a chick survives to fledge) is subsumed into juvenile survival. This is because birds are typically banded soon after hatching and resight data were reported on an annual basis. Thus, estimates of juvenile survival from mark-resight data correspond to the combined probability that an individual both fledged and survived its first winter.

As with adult survival, we used the model-averaged yearly estimates from each site to evaluate whether juvenile apparent survival rates varied among sites or years within a general linear model framework or by nonlinear regression and resulting AICc values to evaluate the support for different linear models describing different hypotheses. We tested models assuming that survival 1) was the same across all sites and years, 2) varied by year but not site, 3) was unusually low in 2006 (corresponding to range-wide reduced adult survival in this year) but did not otherwise vary across years, 4) was lower 2001-2003 than 2004-2012 (as a way to address a general increase in predator management after 2002-2004), 5) varied by latitude (measured as km north of the U.S./Mexico border), 6) varied by site without reference to latitude; we also examined all appropriate 2-way interactions. We included models with linear, exponential and logarithmic relationships between survival and latitude. Because there were large differences among sites in the number of marked juvenile birds used to generate survival estimates, analyses were weighted by sample size (i.e., the number of marked birds used to generate the corresponding annual estimate for a site).

Reproductive effort: Reproductive effort was measured as the mean number of chicks hatched in a breeding season per male breeding at a given site. This parameter is the product of four sub-processes: 1) the percent of males at a site that attempt at least one clutch, 2) the number of eggs per clutch of breeding males, 3) the percent of eggs in a clutch that hatch (hatching success), and 4) the number of clutches attempted by breeding males. Data were the numbers of chicks produced or eggs hatched at a site in a given year divided by number of adult males present at the site in that year. Chick numbers from Monterey Bay were calculated from the number of fledglings divided by the fledging rate (i.e., % marked chicks that fledged). The number of males breeding at a site was determined in various ways at different sites (Table 1).

We used yearly estimates of reproductive effort to evaluate whether reproductive rates varied: 1) among sites, 2) among years, 3) by distance north of Mexico, or 4) by the number or relative density of males breeding at a site. We calculated the relative density of adult plovers as the number of plovers at a site in a given year divided by the maximum number observed from BWS counts at the site at any time from 2005 through 2011. Models were fit to the data using a general linear model framework or by nonlinear regression and resulting AICc values were used to evaluate the support for different linear models describing different hypotheses.

Dispersal: We treated dispersal as a two-step process. First, a bird emigrates from a site where it was hatched (in the case of juvenile dispersal) or where it was last known to breed in previous years (in the case of adult dispersal). That site is considered the dispersing bird's origin, or source. Second, the bird immigrates to another site the following breeding season. The site to which a dispersing bird immigrates is considered the destination site. We did not consider dispersal-related mortality separately from other sources of mortality, in part because data were not available to do so, and in part because it is not clear that dispersing birds moving to "new sites", which may be their overwintering site (Lafferty et al. 2006), faced any greater mortality risk than did birds returning to their site of origin. Dispersal data come from birds banded at one site reported in a subsequent year at another site during the breeding season. In many cases, birds were only reported if they showed signs of attempted breeding. Because estimates of emigration rates used information from distance dispersal curves generated from immigration data, we describe the methods for generating distance dispersal curves and immigration probabilities before describing the methods to estimate emigration rates.

Immigration: Distance-dispersal curves: We estimated immigration rates using distance-dispersal curves of emigrants to monitored sites. The idea is similar to estimating seed dispersal data from counts of seeds in traps established at known distances from potential sources (Clark 2007). In this case, the "seeds" are banded birds observed after immigrating to one of several monitored sites. Each bird represented a successful dispersal event originating from the site where it was banded (or in some cases, known to have last bred) that could have ended at any one of a number of monitored sites. Most data came from immigrants reported from Oregon, Monterey Bay, Oceano Dunes, Vandenberg, and Bolsa Chica, and these five sites constituted the possible destinations. For Monterey Bay and Oregon, if specific destinations were not provided, we used the central breeding site to calculate distances. For the most part, this applied to birds originating far away, and the resulting error had little influence on curve fitting. A third of the data came from birds born in Monterey Bay that subsequently emigrated to one of the other sites surveyed during Breeding Window Surveys. For these data, sources were assigned as one of North, Central or South Bay, depending on what region within Monterey Bay the bird originated, and any of the BWS sites were considered available. The Central Bay was bordered by Reservation Road in Marina to the south and Beach Road in Watsonville to the north. Two birds known to immigrate to inland sites that we could not associate with a BWS site were excluded from this analysis.

The resulting dataset had three pieces of information from each potential source-destination pair: the distance between a potential source and potential destination, the number of birds that emigrated from the source and could have immigrated to and been observed at that destination, and the number of birds originating from that source that were observed to have immigrated to that destination. From these data we calculated for each potential source-destination pair the percentage of birds that could have immigrated to the destination that did ("percent observed"). We binned data into 10 km bins (roughly representing the precision of the data), fit power and exponential curves to the resulting data using nonlinear regression of percent observed vs. distance, weighted by the number of possible observations of birds immigrating a particular distance.

The next step was to assign the likelihood that a bird successfully emigrating from a given source would immigrate to each potential destination site. This likelihood was calculated by applying the regression

equation above to the distance between potential pairs of source and destination sites. We used as the set of potential source and destination sites the populations included in the BWS. Some BWS sites, however, are extremely close and probably represent a single intermixing population (e.g., Gaudalupe Dunes is contiguous with Pismo Beach). We therefore lumped sites with central coordinates ≤ 15 km apart into single units, resulting in a 25 population set covering the U.S. Pacific coast (Table 2). In addition, we calculated the likelihood of birds dispersing to hypothetical sites in Mexico located 5, 15, 20, 35 and 45 km south of the border. These distances were determined from visual inspection of satellite imagery of the Mexican coast on Google Earth and identifying possible breeding sites such as dune-backed wide beaches and river mouth estuaries similar in appearance to known sites on the U.S. coast. Immigration probabilities, given that a bird successfully emigrates from a source, were then calculated for each potential destination by dividing the likelihood of a given source-destination pair by the sum of likelihoods for all possible destinations from a given source. The inclusion of sites in Mexico resulted in the probabilities of successfully dispersing birds landing in a U.S. site summing to < 1 , accounting for potential loss of birds immigrating to Mexico. Immigration to U.S. subpopulations from Mexico was not considered since recovery goals for the U.S. population should not rely on immigration from Mexico.

Emigration rates: The data that were available to estimate emigration rates were especially sparse and varied in how they were collected and reported. Detailed descriptions of rates generated from each site for which data were available are given below.

From Oregon

Juvenile dispersal: we started by calculating the % of fledglings known to survive at least one year that emigrated to monitored sites outside of Oregon (i.e., the number reported from Bolsa Chica, Monterey Bay, Northern California, Oceano Dunes or Vandenberg) as the number of observed emigrants divided by the sum of the number of returning banded fledglings and number of emigrants. A total of 3 out of 252 known survivors emigrated to monitored sites from 2001-2008 (1.2%). The five monitored sites are expected to receive 6.4% of emigrants originating from any of the six Oregon breeding sites. This yields an estimate of 18.8% ($0.012/0.064=0.1875$) of surviving fledglings emigrating elsewhere.

From Northern California

Adult dispersal: we estimated adult dispersal from Pearson and Colwell (2013). We assumed that movements ≤ 10 km were “within site” and that movements > 10 km were emigration events. Using their data for between-year moves of renesting birds, 15% of adults emigrated at least 10 km. Note that 25%-30% of adults moved 1-10 km between seasons, and $\sim 45\%$ within a season.

From Monterey Bay:

Adult dispersal: Taken from Stenzel et al. (1994): 6.03% of adult breeders from 1984-1989 known to disperse to other sites.

Juvenile dispersal: Taken from Stenzel et al. (2007): Estimated emigration rates to sites outside of Monterey Bay during the period 1984-1999 were 40.5% for females and 25.6% for males (average=33.1%). From the Monterey Bay reports and dispersal data provided for birds hatched

between 2001 and 2011, 74 of 881 (8.4%) banded juveniles emigrated from MB in their first year. Dispersal within Monterey Bay sites account for 26.8% of the expected dispersal of birds originating from one of the three Monterey Bay sites, so the 8.4% of banded juveniles dispersing outside Monterey Bay should represent 73.2% of all dispersal, yielding an estimated 12.5% probability that a chick hatched at Monterey Bay survives and emigrates to another site in its first year, and a 4.1% probability that a bird survives and disperses to another site within Monterey Bay. Based on these estimates, $[0.125/(0.125+(0.09-4.1))]=71.8\%$ of surviving juveniles emigrated from their natal site, with 48.3% emigrating to sites outside of Monterey Bay.

From Vandenberg & Oceano Dunes

Juvenile dispersal: For these two sites we used the capture histories provided in reports to estimate the % of banded juveniles that dispersed between these two sites. Of the 1337 broods banded at these sites from 2002-2012, 75 (5.6%) of banded chicks were known to have survived and emigrated by the end of their first breeding season. Another 372 birds survived and were seen (only) at their natal sites through their first year of adulthood, meaning that 16.8% of birds known to survive their first winter emigrated to the other site. Dispersal between the two sites is expected to account for 19.2% of all dispersal originating from either site, which means that an estimated additional 390 juvenile plovers dispersed elsewhere, leading to an estimated 55.5% emigration rate of surviving chicks born at these sites.

From Pendleton

Adult dispersal: From 1994-1999, 9 of 155 (5.8%) banded adults were known to emigrate.

Juvenile dispersal: Over the same time period, 17% of banded fledglings were known to return to and breed in San Diego County. Of these, 70% returned to Camp Pendleton, 26% to Batiquitos, and 4% to Tijuana NWR. Assuming all San Diego County sites were monitored over this period, the 30% of San Diego returning birds that emigrated within the county represent 47% of all expected emigrants. If this represented 30 emigrant birds of 100 known alive, we would expect the total number of emigrants to be $30/0.47=64$ birds out of 70 known from CP $+(64 \text{ known} + \text{estimated emigrants})=134$ birds, yielding an estimated emigration rate of $64/134 = 47.8\%$.

Table 2. Immigration probabilities of dispersing plovers between breeding sites on the U.S. Pacific coast.

SOURCE	DESTINATION												
	SAN DIEGO COUNTY	BATI-QUITOS	SAN NICOLAS	PENDLETON	BOLSA CHICA	SANTA ROSA	MUGU	DEVER-REAUX BEACH	VANDEN-BERG	PISMO BEACH	MORRO BAY	SAN SIMEON	PT SUR
SAN DIEGO COUNTY	-	0.091	0.017	0.073	0.047	0.015	0.030	0.021	0.016	0.011	0.008	0.005	0.003
BATIQUITOS	0.101	-	0.034	0.147	0.094	0.030	0.061	0.043	0.032	0.022	0.015	0.010	0.005
SAN NICOLAS	0.054	0.098	-	0.113	0.072	0.052	0.047	0.033	0.112	0.076	0.053	0.036	0.018
PENDLETON	0.082	0.150	0.039	-	0.119	0.038	0.077	0.054	0.040	0.028	0.019	0.013	0.006
BOLSA CHICA	0.055	0.101	0.027	0.126	-	0.063	0.128	0.090	0.067	0.046	0.032	0.022	0.011
SANTA ROSA	0.027	0.049	0.058	0.060	0.095	-	0.120	0.084	0.140	0.096	0.067	0.046	0.022
MUGU	0.037	0.067	0.018	0.083	0.130	0.081	-	0.141	0.104	0.071	0.050	0.034	0.016
DEVERREAUX BEACH	0.027	0.049	0.013	0.061	0.095	0.059	0.147	-	0.155	0.106	0.074	0.050	0.024
VANDENBERG	0.019	0.035	0.042	0.043	0.068	0.094	0.104	0.148	-	0.137	0.096	0.065	0.031
PISMO BEACH	0.014	0.026	0.031	0.033	0.051	0.071	0.078	0.111	0.150	-	0.154	0.105	0.051
MORRO BAY	0.011	0.020	0.024	0.025	0.039	0.055	0.060	0.086	0.116	0.169	-	0.165	0.080
SAN SIMEON	0.009	0.016	0.019	0.019	0.030	0.042	0.047	0.066	0.089	0.131	0.187	-	0.133
PT SUR	0.005	0.009	0.011	0.011	0.017	0.024	0.027	0.038	0.052	0.075	0.108	0.158	-
MONTEREY	0.003	0.006	0.007	0.008	0.012	0.017	0.018	0.026	0.035	0.052	0.074	0.108	0.224
HALF MOON BAY	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.009	0.013	0.017	0.025	0.036	0.052	0.108
SF BAY	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.009	0.013	0.017	0.025	0.036	0.052	0.108
PT REYES	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.008	0.011	0.016	0.023	0.033	0.069
MACKERRICHER	0	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.006	0.009	0.014	0.028
EEL RIVER	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.005
CLAM BEACH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.003
HUMBOLDT LAGOONS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002
BANDON	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
COOS BAY	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
OREGON NORTH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
WASHINGTON	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2 (cont)

SOURCE	DESTINATION											
	MONTEREY BAY	HALF MOON BAY	SF BAY	PT REYES	MAC-KERRICHER	EEL RIVER	CLAM BEACH	HUMBOLDT LAGOONS	BANDON	COOS BAY	OREGON NORTH	WASHINGTON
SAN DIEGO COUNTY	0.002	0.001	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BATIQUITOS	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SAN NICOLAS	0.011	0.005	0.005	0.002	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PENDLETON	0.004	0.002	0.002	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BOLSA CHICA	0.007	0.003	0.003	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SANTA ROSA	0.014	0.006	0.006	0.003	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MUGU	0.010	0.004	0.004	0.002	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
DEVERREAUX BEACH	0.016	0.007	0.007	0.003	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
VANDENBERG	0.020	0.008	0.008	0.004	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PISMO BEACH	0.032	0.014	0.014	0.007	0.002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MORRO BAY	0.051	0.021	0.021	0.011	0.003	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0
SAN SIMEON	0.085	0.035	0.035	0.018	0.004	0.001	0.001	0.001	0	0	0	0
PT SUR	0.209	0.088	0.088	0.043	0.011	0.003	0.002	0.001	0	0	0	0
MONTEREY	-	0.147	0.147	0.073	0.018	0.004	0.003	0.002	0	0	0	0
HALF MOON BAY	0.170	-	0.262	0.201	0.050	0.012	0.007	0.006	0.001	0.001	0	0
SF BAY	0.170	0.262	-	0.201	0.050	0.012	0.007	0.006	0.001	0.001	0	0
PT REYES	0.107	0.256	0.256	-	0.128	0.030	0.019	0.015	0.002	0.001	0.001	0
MACKERRICHER	0.044	0.105	0.105	0.212	-	0.202	0.126	0.102	0.013	0.009	0.005	0
EEL RIVER	0.007	0.018	0.018	0.035	0.143	-	0.378	0.307	0.040	0.026	0.015	0.001
CLAM BEACH	0.004	0.009	0.009	0.019	0.077	0.329	-	0.430	0.056	0.037	0.021	0.001
HUMBOLDT LAGOONS	0.003	0.008	0.008	0.017	0.067	0.284	0.457	-	0.074	0.048	0.027	0.001
BANDON	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.003	0.011	0.049	0.078	0.096	-	0.477	0.272	0.010
COOS BAY	0	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.007	0.030	0.048	0.058	0.446	-	0.391	0.015
OREGON NORTH	0	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.005	0.022	0.036	0.044	0.336	0.518	-	0.035
WASHINGTON	0	0	0	0.001	0.003	0.012	0.019	0.024	0.180	0.276	0.485	-

Results I. Spatio-Temporal Patterns in Demographic Rates

Adult survival: The top models in the analyses of mark-resight data had constant detection rates across years at all sites except Oceano Dunes, where the top model had detection probabilities that varied annually (probably due to low detection rates in 2007-2008). Detection rates were very high for birds breeding in Monterey Bay and Northern California sites ($p=0.96$ and $p=0.89$, respectively) and considerably lower at other sites ($p=0.65$ in San Francisco Bay, $p=0.57$ at Vandenberg, average $p=0.55$ at Oceano Dunes). The top survival model varied across sites. In Northern California and Monterey Bay, survival varied annually but not by age class. In San Francisco Bay and Oceano Dunes, the top model included variation by class but not year. At Vandenberg, the top model included variation in both year and class. At all sites except Oceano Dunes, there was substantial support (i.e., model likelihoods >0.45 , AIC weight >0.14) for models including annual variation in survival.

The best supported model describing spatio-temporal patterns in adult survival was that adult survival varied by latitude and that survival was abnormally low in 2006 (Table 3, Figure 2). Birds from Oregon appear to be an exception to this pattern, having local adult survival rates higher than predicted by their latitude. Allowing separate

survival estimates for Oregon substantially altered the shape and improved the fit of the best fit curve. There is a suggestion in longer data sets from Monterey and Oregon that 1998-1999 and 1990-1991 were also years with low adult survival (data not shown).

Model-fitted adult survival rates for the 25 sites included

in the PVA are presented in Table 4. The average standard deviation in annual local adult survival estimates was 0.115.

Figure 2. Adult apparent survival vs. distance north. Solid points indicate average survival in "good years" (2005-2006, 2007-2011), open circles survival from 2006-2007. Dashed line indicates best fit regression line excluding Oregon breeding sites.

Table 3. AICc Analysis of spatio-temporal patterns for adult survival.

model	df	AICc	delta AICc	AICc weight
Distance north of Mexico + Oregon + YR=2006	5	-88.8	0	0.971
Distance north of Mexico + Oregon	4	-81.4	7.38	0.024
Oregon + YR=2006	4	-76.8	12.02	0.002
YR=2006	3	-75.6	13.22	0.001
Distance north of Mexico + YR=2006	4	-73.6	15.17	0
Oregon	3	-71.8	17.02	0
NULL	2	-70.8	17.94	0
Distance north of Mexico	3	-68.9	19.89	0

Juvenile survival: There was not a clear indication that juvenile survival varied among sites or that any given year was characterized by low juvenile survival across all sites. Average juvenile survival across all sites and years was $s_{juv}=0.188 \pm 0.105$ std.

Reproductive effort: There was a tight correlation between fecundity (chicks hatched/male during a breeding season) and an exponential decay function with increasing latitude (Figure 3).

Distance-dispersal curves: An exponential curve fit the data significantly better than a power curve. Distance dispersal curves were very similar between juvenile and adult emigrants, so data were combined to generate the final distance dispersal curve (Figure 4).

Emigration rates: Because of the variety of methods and many assumptions made to estimate emigration from the small number of sites from which data were available, we did not look for spatial or temporal patterns in emigration rates. The probability that an individual survived and emigrated estimated from all available data was 0.063 for juveniles and 0.08 for adults.

Figure 3. Fecundity plotted against distance north of Mexico. Points indicate the average annual chicks per male produced at each site. Dashed line shows best fit nonlinear regression curve.

Figure 4. Distance dispersal curve for snowy plovers along the U.S. Pacific Coast. Each bubble shows the percent of emigrating birds which could have been observed dispersing between two sites that were observed immigrating to the corresponding destination site given its distance from the site of origin. The size of each bubble indicates the number of potential dispersers (i.e., the sample size) used to weight the nonlinear regression. The line depicts the best fit nonlinear regression curve.

Deterministic model:

Once spatio-temporal patterns in demographic rates were determined, the next step was to build a deterministic metapopulation model. This model had two components: a set of site-specific population projection models, and a set of links to account for the influence of dispersal. We used the reduced 25 population set created during the distance-dispersal analysis in all models. If we assume that reproduction is limited by males and an equal sex ratio at birth, the site-specific project model takes the form:

$$n_{p,t+1} = n_{p,t} * (s_{ad}[d_p, OR] + \frac{1}{2}f[d_p] * s_{juv}) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $n_{s,t}$ is the number of adult males for population p at the beginning of the breeding season in year t,
- s_{ad} is the adult survival for population p determined as a function of the distance (d_p) the site is north of the U.S.-Mexico border, adjusted for Oregon sites (OR),
- $\frac{1}{2}f$ is the average number of male chicks produced per male breeding in population p determined as a function of the distance the site is north of the U.S.-Mexico border, and
- s_{juv} is juvenile.

The expected long term growth rate at each site in the absence of density dependence and dispersal is given by:

$$\lambda = (s_{ad}[d_p, OR] + \frac{1}{2}f[d_p] * s_{juv}). \quad (2)$$

Equation 1 represents the predicted growth potential of a population at “average” population density (Table 4). While the functional form of equation 1 is the same for typical (“good”) years and years like 2006 during which survival was depressed (“bad years”), different values of s_{ad} would be applied to describe population growth in bad years and the long term expected growth rate will depend on the frequency of bad years. Latitudinal clines in both adult survival and chick production resulted in a latitudinal cline in growth potential (Figures 5-6), with most populations south of Point Reyes acting as sources (i.e., would exhibit positive growth in isolation) and most populations north acting as sinks (i.e., would shrink in the absence of immigration). In “bad” years, only the southernmost populations would be expected not to shrink in the absence of immigrants.

Dispersal was added to the deterministic model by adding net dispersal rates to the predicted growth rate at each site. Net adult dispersal rates for each site were calculated as:

$$e_a * \sum_{p \neq f} \frac{s_p}{s_f} i_{p,f}$$

Where e_a is the adult emigration rate, f is the focal population, p are the 24 other populations, s_f and s_p are the adult survival rates in populations f and p, respectively, and $i_{f,p}$ is the probability that an emigrant from population p immigrates to population f. Net juvenile dispersal rates for each site were calculated as:

$$e_j * \sum_{p \neq f} \frac{r_p}{r_f} i_{p,f}$$

Where e_j is the juvenile emigration rate, f is the focal population, p are the 24 other populations, r_f and r_p are the average number of chicks per male in populations f and p , respectively, and $i_{f,p}$ is the probability that an emigrant from population p immigrates to population f .

Site “connectivity” (Figure 7) can be measured for each site as:

$$c = e_a * \sum_{p \neq f} \frac{s_f}{s_p} i_{f,p} + e_j * \sum_{p \neq f} \frac{r_f}{r_p} i_{f,p}. \quad (3)$$

The sum, $\lambda + c$, represents the expected growth potential of each site accounting for dispersal, and is presented in Table 4 and Figure 6.

The next step was to incorporate density dependence into the model. We accomplished this by comparing the difference between the observed population growth at a site and that predicted by the deterministic model (i.e., growth rate residuals) to the relative density at that site. We calculated the growth rate residuals as the difference between observed annual changes in plover numbers from the 2005-2011 BWS counts and the regression line for projected growth rate for each site. These residuals represent the difference between the observed population growth rate at a site and what would be expected if the deterministic model above was correct, with each population being represented six times.

Because of difficulties accurately measuring the area of quality breeding habitat at each site, exacerbated by lack of information about what habitat variables limit population size at a breeding site, accurate direct measures of population density through time were not available. The best information we had was adult counts from annual breeding window surveys. If we assume that detection rates at each site were similar from year to year, these counts give a reasonable index of relative densities across years within each site. However, because some sites are capable of supporting greater numbers of plovers than others, BWS counts do not reflect comparable measures of relative densities across sites. To account for these site differences, we had to further assume that the largest number of plovers observed at a site from 2005-2011 was proportional to the carrying capacity of the site. Under these assumptions, the ratio of the BWS count at a site in a given year to the maximum observed BWS count at that site yields an index of the relative density of plovers at a site that is comparable across sites and years. Population growth rates following the year the maximum BWS count was observed at a site were excluded from further analysis, by definition, those growth rates could only be negative. Years in which there were fewer than two plovers observed at a site were also excluded, since any positive growth in such years would be solely due to immigration. Because we suspected that density dependence might act differently at sites at different latitudes, several models fitting residual growth rates to the relative density and distance north of the U.S.-Mexico border were evaluated. Models were fit using nonlinear regression in R and accepted the model with the lowest AICc value. The best fit model indicated that predicted growth rates would be improved by including both a correction factor for latitude and density dependence (Table 5; Figure 8).

Figure 5. Expected population growth rates in the absence of immigrants for 25 subpopulations along the U.S. Pacific coast.

Figure 6. Expected population growth rate of 25 subpopulations plotted against distance north of Mexico. Top panel shows expected subpopulation growth rates in typical “good” (high adult survival; solid circles) and bad (low adult survival; open circles) years in the absence of immigration. Bottom panel shows the same after accounting for immigration.

Table 4. Subpopulation summaries.

AREA	recovery unit	distance north of Mexico	BWS mean	BWS max	mean relative density	male chicks per male	local adult survival		local juvenile survival	isolated growth potential (λ)		connected growth potential (λ)			
							good years	bad years		good years	bad years	adult net disp	juv net disp	good years	bad years
WASHINGTON	1	1575	44.3	70	0.63	1.23	0.51	0.40	0.19	0.75	0.63	0.07	0.07	0.90	0.79
OREGON NORTH	1	1246	59.7	119	0.50	1.30	0.69	0.57	0.19	0.93	0.82	1.19	1.21	1.30	1.18
COOS BAY	1	1206	32.6	41	0.79	1.31	0.69	0.58	0.19	0.94	0.83	1.36	1.38	0.97	0.85
BANDON	1	1163	34.4	41	0.84	1.33	0.70	0.58	0.19	0.95	0.84	1.12	1.14	0.90	0.79
HUMBOLDT LAGOONS	2	963	1.7	7	0.24	1.39	0.63	0.52	0.19	0.90	0.78	1.09	1.10	1.53	1.41
CLAM BEACH	2	942	14.3	22	0.65	1.40	0.64	0.52	0.19	0.90	0.79	1.18	1.18	1.06	0.94
EEL RIVER	2	899	8.9	22	0.40	1.42	0.65	0.53	0.19	0.92	0.80	0.98	0.99	1.34	1.23
MACKERRICHER	2	752	2.6	9	0.29	1.48	0.68	0.56	0.19	0.96	0.84	0.58	0.59	1.47	1.36
PT REYES	4	620	25.3	41	0.62	1.55	0.70	0.58	0.19	1.00	0.88	0.86	0.88	1.12	1.00
SF BAY	3	553	173.1	269	0.64	1.60	0.71	0.60	0.19	1.02	0.90	1.00	1.02	1.10	0.98
HALF MOON BAY	4	545	2.7	7	0.39	1.61	0.72	0.60	0.19	1.02	0.90	1.00	1.02	1.41	1.29
MONTEREY	4	468	269.0	368	0.73	1.67	0.73	0.61	0.19	1.05	0.93	0.97	0.99	1.00	0.89
PT SUR	5	415	7.6	13	0.58	1.72	0.74	0.63	0.19	1.07	0.95	0.94	0.98	1.18	1.07
SAN SIMEON	5	343	5.4	15	0.36	1.80	0.76	0.64	0.19	1.10	0.98	0.98	1.02	1.46	1.34
MORRO BAY	5	310	153.4	262	0.59	1.85	0.76	0.65	0.19	1.11	1.00	1.04	1.10	1.20	1.08
PISMO BEACH	5	270	182.4	214	0.85	1.92	0.77	0.65	0.19	1.13	1.02	1.09	1.16	0.89	0.77
VANDENBERG	5	240	203.3	272	0.75	1.97	0.78	0.66	0.19	1.15	1.03	1.16	1.23	1.02	0.90
DEVERREAUX BEACH	5	203	35.7	48	0.74	2.06	0.78	0.67	0.19	1.17	1.06	0.97	1.01	1.01	0.90
MUGU	5	174	125.4	165	0.76	2.14	0.79	0.67	0.19	1.20	1.08	0.96	1.00	1.00	0.88
SANTA ROSA	5	158	14.6	37	0.39	2.19	0.79	0.68	0.19	1.21	1.09	0.65	0.65	1.41	1.29
BOLSA CHICA	6	125	53.6	66	0.81	2.33	0.80	0.68	0.19	1.24	1.12	0.88	0.89	0.93	0.81
PENDLETON	6	81	126.1	169	0.75	2.60	0.81	0.69	0.19	1.30	1.18	0.80	0.78	1.01	0.89
SAN NICOLAS	5	77	61.9	96	0.64	2.63	0.81	0.69	0.19	1.31	1.19	0.34	0.30	1.10	0.98
BATIQUITOS	6	59	7.9	14	0.56	2.81	0.81	0.69	0.19	1.34	1.23	0.71	0.65	1.23	1.11
SAN DIEGO COUNTY	6	7	76.9	129	0.60	4.50	0.82	0.71	0.19	1.68	1.56	0.43	0.27	1.23	1.11

Figure 7. Site connectedness measured as per-capita relative dispersal rates (expected immigrants/expected emigrants assuming all populations are the same size). Darker shades indicate sites with higher per capita immigration than emigration rates. Shading of San Diego County sites reflects emigrants to Mexico but not immigrants from south of the border.

Table 5. AICc Analysis of density dependence in population growth.

model ¹	df	AICc	delta AICc
resid~x+ln(NDN)	3	84.17	0
resid~x+NDN	4	90.91	6.74
resid~x+x*NDN	5	91.87	7.7
resid~x+NDN+NDN*NDN	5	91.91	7.74
resid~x	3	98.68	14.51
resid~NDN	3	120.56	36.39

1. x=relative plover density, NDN=km north of Mexican border

Note that while the maximum observed BWS count at each site was used as an index of a site’s carrying capacity in this analysis, it is not assumed to be the carrying capacity.

Corrected predicted growth rates for each site accounting for dispersal and density dependence are presented in Table 4. The expected metapopulation growth from 2005-2011 was calculated as the average population growth rate at each site weighted by the average population size observed at the site as determined by the BWS (Table 6). Compared to the observed average metapopulation growth rates in good (2005-2006, 2007-2011) years, the deterministic projection model was biased slightly low when populations were considered in isolation, whereas the connected model was biased high (Figure 9). Adding in the correction for density dependence resulted in a close match between projected and mean observed population growth in good years (Figure 9). All projected growth rates for 2006-2007

Figure 8. Density dependence in observed population growth. Points indicate the difference between the observed and expected population growth at each subpopulation plotted against the relative density of the site in that year. Subpopulations are divided between those further or closer than 400 km north of the Mexican border to illustrate latitudinal effect on the relationship.

were higher than the observed metapopulation growth. We also compared the density corrected model metapopulation growth projections to independent data from the 2012 and 2013 BWS surveys. The model projected greater than observed declines in the metapopulation for both 2011-2012 and 2012-2013 given the starting BWS population size in each subpopulation in each year. However, the two year projection, using projected subpopulation densities in 2012 to project the 2013 population size, was very similar to the observed change in the population from 2011 to 2013 (Figure 9).

Simulation Model- Methods

Environmental and demographic stochasticity were incorporated into the model through simulation. The simulation model assumed 25 populations corresponding to the 25 sites determined from dispersal analysis. These sites were initially populated with a number of adult plovers equal to the average population size recorded in BWS counts from 2005-2011, rounded to the nearest integer.

The first step in the simulation was to determine the demographic rates realized at each site in the first year. Demographic rates were drawn from a normal distribution with mean taken from Table 4 and approximate standard deviation estimated from the annual variation in survival and reproductive rates from the demographic analyses (std adult survival=0.1; std juvenile survival=0.1, std chick production=0.5*mean chick production-0.61). Each year, there was a 90% chance that mean survival rates corresponded to “good” years and a 10% chance that mean survival rates corresponded to “bad” years. The standard deviation in emigration rates was set to 0.01, which was approximately the same proportional variance relative to the expected value as was observed in the other demographic rates. Realized demographic rates were adjusted to ensure that: survival rates (survive & stay + survive & emigrate) were between 0 and 1, and average reproductive output at a site was constrained to 0-9 chicks/male.

Once the time-specific (realized) demographic rates at each site were determined, the number of adults in each site was multiplied by:

- the adult survival rate to yield the number of adults surviving and returning to the site the following year;
- the product of the average number of chicks per male and juvenile survival to yield the number of juveniles recruited to the population the following year;
- the adult emigration rate yielding the number of potential adult emigrants to other sites the following year; and
- the product of the number of chicks per male and juvenile emigration rate to yield the number of potential juvenile emigrants to other sites the following year.

The pre-dispersal population at each site the following year was then calculated as the number of adults returning plus the number of juveniles recruited to the population (equation 1). The population size was then adjusted by the effect of density dependence at the site with the constraint that it remained ≥ 0 . The effect of density dependence was modeled as an addition or subtraction of birds according to the equation:

$$\text{adj} = -1.19 * N / \text{BWS}_{\text{max}} + 0.123 * \ln(\text{km North of Mexico}) \quad (5)$$

Where N is the number of birds in the population at the beginning of the time step and BWS_{max} is the maximum number of birds observed at the site in the 2005-2011 BWS surveys.

The final action in each time step was to add dispersers to each site. Emigrants from each site were randomly assigned to immigrate to another site according to the dispersal probabilities in Table 2. While immigrants from Mexico were not considered in the simulation, emigrants could potentially migrate to Mexico, and were subsequently considered lost to the U.S. population.

These steps were repeated for 50 (annual) time steps for each replicate of the simulation. At the end of each time step the total number of adults in the metapopulation was recorded. The number of adults in each site at the end of each time step and percent of adults that had immigrated to the site that year was recorded for a representative replicate for each simulation treatment.

To test the sensitivity of predicted plover population size to demographic rates we varied adult survival, juvenile survival and the average chicks per male from between -30% to + 30% of their baseline values in 10% increments. Sensitivity tests on survival included adjustments to both the probability a bird survived and stayed at a site and the probability a bird survived and emigrated. Elasticity rates were calculated as the proportional change relative to baseline simulations in the average total number of adults in the metapopulation averaged over 50 years divided by the proportional change in the demographic rate being tested. To test the sensitivity to assumptions about the magnitude of stochasticity put into the model, we doubled the standard deviation used to draw annual realized rates for all demographic parameters.

We also ran several modifications of the simulation to test model assumptions and explore possible effects of habitat loss and restoration. To determine the impact of dispersal on plover metapopulation dynamics we ran simulations with no dispersal. To examine the effects of habitat loss and restoration we conducted several simulated “experiments.” We removed each site from the simulation to determine the impact losing individual sites would have on plover metapopulation dynamics. We also simulated a range-wide 0.5% per year decrease in the carrying capacity of all sites as a crude measure of the potential impact of habitat loss impacting the entire coast due to the combined effects of sea level rise, beach erosion and development. Finally, we simulated habitat restoration to each site by substituting $(BWS_{max}+100)$ for BWS_{max} in equation 5.

We ran 150 replicates of the baseline simulation, 100 replicates of simulations with high variance and range-wide habitat loss, and 50 replicates of all other simulations.

Simulation Model- Results

The simulation indicated that the Pacific coast plover population is likely to be quite stable, fluctuating around ~1900-2000 birds (Figure 10). Sensitivity analysis indicates that predicted average metapopulation size was most sensitive to adult survival, which had about twice as large an effect on model outcome as chick production rates and juvenile survival (Figure 10). Population declines associated with reduced fecundity or survivorship tended to happen within the first few years after which the average metapopulation size remained constant. Doubling the amount of environmental stochasticity experienced by the population led to a relatively small reduction in the mean metapopulation size across all replicates, but had a large effect on both the year to year fluctuations in

population size and the uncertainty of model predictions (i.e., differences among replicate runs of the simulation, Figure 10). Nonetheless, the mean projected metapopulation size in high variance runs was still stable through time, and no simulated metapopulations dipped below 950 breeding plovers. The only treatments that led to continuing metapopulation decline were removing dispersal and imposing a continuous range-wide habitat loss (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Baseline simulation projections and sensitivity analysis. Top panel shows the mean of 150 replicate simulated population projections through 50 years. Minimum and maximum values of baseline simulations for each time step are shown, but lines overlap with mean line. Simulations with different mean parameter values behaved much like baseline simulations, differing only in the mean metapopulation size as shown in bottom panel.

Sites varied in their importance to maintaining the metapopulation size, with the destruction of larger populations leading to greater reduction in metapopulation size (Figure 12). Thus even sites projected to be sink habitat based on their demographic rates play an important role in maintaining and recovering snowy plovers if they represent sufficient protected habitat. Habitat restoration increased the average metapopulation size

Figure 11. Projected plover metapopulation dynamics in simulations without dispersal (top panel) or with constant range-wide habitat loss (bottom panel).

regardless of where habitat was restored, but the magnitude of the effect varied among sites (Figure 13). Unlike habitat destruction, the sites where habitat restoration might have the greatest impact were not necessarily the largest, or smallest, sites. Restoration had the highest impact at those sites with high projected growth rates after accounting for dispersal (Figure 13).

Figure 12. Change in mean projected metapopulation size associated with loss of a subpopulation site. Top panel indicates reduction in metapopulation size projected with removal of the site indicated on the X-axis. Bottom panel shows plot of metapopulation reduction against the index of relative population carrying capacity of the site removed from the simulation.

Figure 13. Gain in mean metapopulation size with habitat restoration equivalent to adding 100 plovers to maximum observed BWS survey when applying density dependence. Bottom panel plots the gain in mean metapopulation size plotted against the population growth potential accounting for dispersal of the site to which habitat was added.

Discussion

Latitudinal gradients in both adult survival and fecundity produced a latitudinal gradient in population growth potential, whereby populations in southern California had a higher potential growth rate than those further north. As a result of this gradient, plover population dynamics may be better described, and managed, as a source-sink population rather than classic metapopulation (Harrison and Taylor 1997). However, provided all populations are connected through dispersal, nearly all sites in the historic range have potential for positive growth at low densities under current management regimes. The apparent exceptions, sites in northern California and Washington, have both supported only small plover populations in recent years. These sites also lack predator management, which by virtue of having been in practice at all sites used to estimate model parameters except northern California, is implicitly assumed in our model. The combination of large, intensively managed source populations within southern and central California results in a very low risk of extinction over the next 50 years under current levels of environmental variability.

Managing plovers within a source-sink context would represent a different approach than advocated by the current recovery plan. The change in approach is motivated by differences in our modeling effort compared to the pva used in support of the current recovery criteria. First, the pva used to establish current recovery criteria assumed that the only difference among recovery units that affected demographic rates was predator management (Nur et al. 1999). The analyses in this report indicate that recovery units also differ in latitudinally driven environmental conditions influencing demographic rates. Most of the subpopulations used in the demographic analyses were intensively managed for predators, minimizing the influence of differences in management on parameter estimates. The exception, northern California, does exhibit lower than expected fecundity for its latitude, highlighting the importance of predator management at other sites as a contributing factor to the stability of the plover metapopulation predicted by our simulations (Figure 2). A potential driver of the observed spatial patterns in demographic rates is latitudinal changes in seasonality. For example, breeding tends to start earlier in the year and the breeding season tends to last longer at lower latitudes (Figure 14), potentially allowing adults

Figure 14. Latitudinal correlations with the mean onset (diamonds) and length (squares) of plover breeding season. Data compiled from monitoring reports from Washington, Oregon, San Francisco Bay, Monterey Bay, Vandenberg AFB, Bolsa Chica, Pendleton MCB and NB Coronado. Lines show best fit quadratic curve.

more opportunities to attempt multiple clutches. Similarly, milder winter temperatures at lower latitudes may influence adult survival either directly through reduced mortality risk for birds overwintering at or near breeding sites, or through reduced migration rates and associated migration related mortality risks. The comparatively high adult survival rates in Oregon (given its latitude) are likely at least partially an artifact of the scale at which data are reported. All other data used to estimate adult survival came from re-sight data at a single subpopulation, the two largest covering Monterey and San Francisco bays. In contrast, Oregon return rates included birds at any of the Oregon sites, covering over 450 km of coastline.

Whether the latitudinal gradients in demographic rates are driven by reduced seasonality or some other environmental factor, the consequence is that populations further north will have to be managed substantially more intensively than southern populations in order to achieve the same demographic goals. At the same time, if reduced management or climate change resulted in a reduction of population growth rates in southern populations to the point they were no longer strong sources (i.e., no longer had a growth potential $\gg 1$) this would have serious negative consequences for the overall plover population. Our analyses do not contradict the conclusions of Nur et al. that an average of 1 fledgling per male per season is sufficient reproduction to produce a stable population. They do, however, suggest that applying a singular demographic target across the range is not the most appropriate strategy for conserving and recovering the species. Rather, the inherent source-sink structure of the plover metapopulation should be recognized and accounted for with higher productivity targets in southern recovery units than in northern units.

The second critical difference between our model and the Nur et al. model is the implementation of density dependence. The Nur et al. model assumed that population growth was not influenced by density dependence except that populations were not allowed to exceed a maximum size. In contrast, we found evidence that plover population growth rates decline approximately linearly with increasing density (Figure 8), as would be expected under logistic population growth. Although we did not determine the mechanisms through which density dependence acts on plover populations, if plover reproductive rates decline at high relative densities (e.g., Rodenhouse et al. 2003) demographic criteria for recovery— in particular the one fledgling/male/year criteria stated in the recovery plan— may not be appropriate targets for sites at their carrying capacity. As populations recover, a clearer understanding of how density dependence acts on plover populations is critical to differentiate between relatively low demographic rates at a site reflecting a population approaching carrying capacity from one experiencing a threat and in need of more intensive management.

Our implementation of density dependence resulted in simulations never approaching the recovery target of 3000 plovers, even in scenarios with high adult survival or reproductive output. In contrast, in high reproductive output scenarios implemented by Nur et al., populations had a 57%-82% chance of reaching the 3000 plover target within 25 years. The difference in model predictions was not related to differences in growth potential; our simulations exhibited more rapid population increases over the first few years than did the Nur et al. models. With the strong caveat that the analyses presented here reflect a very poor understanding of how density dependence acts on plover subpopulations, our results imply that achieving a target metapopulation size of 3000 adult plovers will require a substantial addition of

high quality habitat- including the conversion of marginal habitat to high quality habitat through predator management. Effective habitat restoration will be particularly important if sea level rise associated with global climate change, coastal development and other forms of habitat conversion lead to widespread habitat loss (Galbraith et al. 2002, Caldwell and Segal 2007).

As with all modeling exercises, our results depend on several assumptions. Clearly one limitation was that monitoring at most sites, particularly in southern California, is not designed to measure demographic rates through time. However, general patterns in demographic rates hold within data subsets based on geography or methodological differences, and simulation results were robust to slight changes in parameter values. Similar to Nur et al., simulation results did exhibit a greater sensitivity to adult survival than either fecundity or juvenile survival, highlighting that predator protection of nests or chicks will be counterproductive if methods put adults at greater risk (Hardy and Colwell 2008).

As mentioned above, the implementation of density dependence in the model is based on several assumptions required to estimate the effect, most of which are likely violated to some degree. In particular, the relationship between the maximum observed plover population size from BWS surveys and a site's true carrying capacity probably varies from site to site. A better understanding of the abiotic (e.g., area, distance to rivers and streams; MacDonald et al. 2010) and biotic influences (e.g., predation pressure or the presence of breeding marine mammals) that limit plover nesting and chick rearing sites would facilitate more effective habitat restoration efforts and lead to an improved predictive ability of future modeling efforts.

Dispersal is another poorly understood process included in the model. Two assumptions of dispersal in particular likely do not hold for plovers. First, we assumed that emigration rates were constant across years and among sites. It is, however, quite likely that emigration rates increase with density (Denno and Peterson 1995, Matthysen 2005) and are influenced by other environmental factors that also affect other demographic processes (e.g., O'Connor et al. 2007). Secondly, we assumed that individual plovers breed in a single location each year, though there are records of birds attempting one or more nests in wintering grounds before dispersing to a second site to attempt second broods (Stenzel et al. 1994, Pearson and Colwell 2013). Intra-seasonal migration could lead to biased estimates of chick production in sites where the number of breeding males was estimated from the number of simultaneously active nests (Table 1) if net migration occurs before peak nesting activity. Further research on the frequency and impact of these dispersal behaviors on plover population dynamics is likely to be a fruitful topic for guiding plover management and recovery. Frequent intra- and inter-annual dispersal by plovers also means that accurate measures of dispersal rates will allow local managers to better determine the effectiveness of onsite management activities.

Our research points to two additional research agendas with high value to plover recovery. The first is a cost-benefit analysis to habitat restoration. While it is clear that habitat restoration is likely to be a critical component of both achieving target metapopulation size and mitigating losses due to development or sea level rise, it is less clear how and where to most effectively restore plover habitat. Effective restoration will require protecting and restoring environmental conditions suitable for breeding (MacDonald et al. 2010) and recruiting plovers to colonize restored sites. The value of a restored site to the coastal metapopulation will depend largely on its location relative both to other

breeding populations and to plover wintering sites (Lafferty et al. 2006). Sites further south may be expected to contribute more plovers due to higher potential growth rates. However, restoration may be more feasible and less costly further north, and restoration sites that promote dispersal to relatively isolated populations in Washington and northern California may stabilize these populations. Striking the right balance between weighing cost, potential population growth, and connectivity issues will require a focused research effort.

Finally, management and recovery of any endangered species will require attention to and possibly mitigating the effects of global climate change. Climate change could have both positive and negative effects on plovers. On the negative side, intertidal and beach habitats are likely to be lost through sea level rise, increased erosion and reduced sand replenishment (Galbraith et al. 2002, Caldwell and Segal 2007). In addition, projections of increased severe winter storms may lead to increased adult and juvenile overwinter mortality. On the other hand, warmer winter temperatures may lengthen breeding seasons or reduce adult mortality risks at northern latitudes. Managing to maximize future plover population size will require both specific knowledge of how local habitats are expected to change in future environments and how plover demographic rates are influenced by climate drivers.

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